

Empowered learning in school: A scoping review

Anto Titus¹, Peter Varkey Muttungal²

¹Department of Education, Christ University, Bengaluru, India

²Department of Education, Faculty of Arts and Humanities, Christ University, Bengaluru, India

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ABSTRACT

A high degree of motivation, a sense of commitment, self-efficacy and the ability to make the right choices are the characteristics of empowered learners. With education being seen as preparation for life, educators are increasingly pressured to develop curriculum and pedagogy that assist learners to become empowered. Based on the theoretical framework developed by Arksey and O'Malley, the present study reviewed 16 empowered learning intervention studies at the school level published between the years 1995 and 2021 as well as provides an extensive summary of empowered learning enhancing interventions conducted in schools. This study highlights the concept of empowered learning, features and scope of interventions directed towards empowered learning of students at schools and the role of empowered learning in schools. Notwithstanding varied intervention results, the findings of this study indicate that empowered learning interventions produce highly motivated students with a sense of commitment and self-efficacy. This review also identifies the need for more pure experimental studies and a commonly accepted theory on empowered learning as a single concept.

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Corresponding Author:

Anto Titus

Department of Education, St. Francis PU College, Christ University

Hosur Rd, Bhavani Nagar, S.G. Palya, Bengaluru, Karnataka 560029, India

Email: titusanto@gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

Highly empowered individuals possess several self-reliant abilities such as a high degree of self-efficacy, a sense of personal control and a fundamental self-confidence that success results from effective use of one's skills. Researchers' interest in empowerment gained momentum after Zimmerman [1] developed a framework of psychological empowerment characterized by motivation, decision making and problem-solving skills, analytical awareness and participatory behavior. In addition, Walker [2] examined that empowerment is closely associated with an individual's openness to accepting individual differences and the readiness to learn from each other. Empowered learning settings facilitate opportunities to develop and foster innate competencies of learners [3]. The notion of empowerment has become a familiar slogan in education, and a voluminous body of researchers has explored and confirmed the possibility of schools becoming potential locations to enhance empowerment in students [4], [5]. A student empowerment model developed by Kirk *et al.* [6] identified a genuine teacher-student relationship, impartial teacher-student role, and a community consciousness within the classroom as the basic characteristics of a classroom that influences student empowerment.

Mutually shared common goals, the consciousness of community, decision-making through shared power and meaningful activities make schools agents of empowerment [5], [7], [8]. Empowerment occurs when disempowered students attain the power required to realize and fulfil their individual needs and to

collaborate with others to accomplish a common goal [9]. Learning and student empowerment are closely associated and an empowered learner finds a task meaningful and feels a sense of motivation and competence to perform a task that has an impact in a given context. Though it has been argued that teachers are faced with a challenge to figure out ways and means to turn the classroom into an environment that provides intrinsic motivation to students to improve the quality of their learning [10], Leonard *et al.* [11] asserted that an empowering atmosphere can be created in the school by complimenting student efforts and achievements; giving due consideration to the ideas of students; acknowledging and appreciating student creativity and delegating equitable responsibilities to students.

Student empowerment is a gradual process requiring the educators to ensure that the students undergo the process of empowerment not as a burden [12]. Learners can also be empowered through a combined innovative and traditional method of assessment of their knowledge and abilities [13]. This assessment, in turn, empowers learners to act and evaluate their works both as an individual and as a group, review the academic evaluation process and suggest evaluation practices that are different from those proposed [14]. Learning becomes profound when learners feel empowered [15], and this sense of empowerment motivates learners towards knowledge construction rather than information reception.

There is a dearth in knowledge among educationists about the myriads ways of facilitating empowered learning in schools. Scoping review is one of the methods of finding, assembling, and synthesizing relevant information about empowered learning from prevailing literature. The current literature shows scanty evidence of scoping reviews on empowered learning. Therefore, the present study was conducted in tune with the objective of providing educationists relevant knowledge on empowered learning. While previous researchers have paid less attention to review experimental studies on empowered learning, based on Arksey and O' Malley's five-stage framework [16], our aim was first to search and identify documents related to experimental interventions on empowered learning in schools and then to review them. This study also aimed at identifying different conceptualizations of empowered learning; reporting in details various findings related to methodology across the reviewed studies and role of empowered learning in schools. The results of this review and recommendations can ultimately facilitate educationists in implementing empowered learning programs in schools.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This scoping review has its base in Arksey O'Malley's five-stage methodological framework [16] which is iterative with each stage requiring researchers to reflect and repeat steps, when necessary, to ensure comprehensive coverage of literature. This five-stage framework allows rigor, transparency and reliability in each stage of the process and guides new researchers by ensuring replication: i) Identifying the research question; ii) Identifying the relevant studies; iii) Study selection; iv) Charting data; and v) Collating, summarizing and reporting the results are the five stages of the review of the empowered learning of students in schools.

2.1. Identifying the research question

In order to investigate the pivotal elements of the various interventions on empowered learning of students in the class and their effect on students and to capture a broad and inclusive range of literature pertaining to this study, we identified the following questions: i) How is empowered learning conceptualized within the literature pertaining to school-level education?; ii) What are the features and scope of the interventions directed towards the empowered learning of students at school level education?; and iii) How is the role of students' empowered learning within school level education viewed by the researchers in general?

2.2. Identifying relevant studies

In tune with Arksey and O' Malley's recommendations [16], to provide wide coverage to the review, we developed search terms related to interventions on empowered learning of students at school level education. Expertise from a university, librarian and three professors competent in scoping review was sought to identify databases, registers and other sources rich in content to yield search results, refine the key search terms and check the possibility of missing potential data. There were 1,684 studies identified in the final search that was implemented between 13th and 30th of June 2021 in several sources: ProQuest research library (n=174), Microsoft academics (n=257), PubMed (n=235), Google scholar (n=319), JSTOR (n=272), EBSCO (n=120) and ERIC (n=287). For additional potential data (n=20), reference sections and reviews of identified studies were searched.

Boolean connectors were applied to narrow, broaden and combine literature search terms: school, empowerment, learning, method or their equivalent. The search string was narrowly defined in order to avoid irrelevant literature overweighing the literature intended for the study [17]. Focusing on search-specificity,

the search method was also customized, altered, and filters were applied as per each database's explicit search prerequisite, which covered comprehensive content-centric literature.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria are determined generally by the coverage, goal and focus of the review [18]. For this study, inclusion and exclusion criteria were developed to maintain the comprehensiveness of the required data and consider time and monetary limitations [19]. The selection criteria were adhered to at the beginning of the selection process and during the close examination of the studies. Since the researchers' sustained attention to empowerment as a value increased considerably after Zimmerman [1] developed a framework of the nomological network of psychological empowerment, the studies published between the years 1995 and 2021 were considered suitable. Since only studies written in English were considered for the review due to time and monetary constraints, potential data may have been ignored. However, the reference section of the studies reviewed indicates only studies conducted in English. Table 1 shows the inclusion and exclusion criteria of this review.

Table 1. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
- Studies conducted post1995	- Grey literature, opinions, reviews and editorials
- Study population of school students	- Theses, working papers, white papers
- Full paper accessible, unpublished works	- Non-intervention studies
- English publication	- Non-English publications
- Published in peer-reviewed journals	- Interventions conducted in pre-schools and primary schools
- Intervention studies	

2.3. Study selection

Using a prearranged search string, 1,664 studies from the database and 20 studies from other sources were initially identified, which were subsequently narrowed down with the help of EndNote citation software. A total of 405 duplicates were identified and removed from the list. Consecutively, the keyword filter of the titles of the remaining 1,279 studies revealed that 775 of them did not meet the inclusion criteria as they had no relevance to the context (school-based intervention) (n=359), no resemblance (n=416) to the search terms. After an extensive review of the individual titles and abstract of the remaining 504 papers, 488 of them were excluded as they were outside the range of the time period or population or were non-interventional studies. The remaining 16 articles were considered for the study as they met all the inclusion criteria. After a wide reading of these articles, we obtained the full version of these articles and confirmed their appropriateness to the study. Preferred reporting of items for systematic reviews and meta-analysis (PRISMA) statement was used as shown in Figure 1 to select the articles [20].

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram of article selection

2.4. Data charting

The data was charted in alignment with the fourth step of Arksey and O'Malley's framework of scoping review [16]. The researchers developed summaries of each study pertaining to the author(s), year, location of the study, intervention, method and design of the research and results. The summary of the information is given in Table 2.

Table 2. Summary of the included studies

Ref./Location	Intervention	Methodology and design	Results
[21], Nigeria	Five weeks intervention	Quasi-experiment with control and experiment groups; multistage sampling; pre-test/post-test	Significant statistical difference found in the interest and achievement in history in experiment group; participants were empowered with imaginary ability.
[22], Israel	Eight months multi-generational connection program (MCP) on digital education empowerment	Quasi-experiment, pre-test/post-test quantitative and qualitative measure with two intervention groups	Findings reveal that the seniors and children showed more signs of getting closer, increased confidence and competence level.
[23], Norway	Two years of intervention on technology aided classroom	Quasi-experiment no treatment control; Post-test only	Participants who used laptops showed enhanced critical reflection, motivation, self-efficacy and knowledge empowerment.
[24], Taiwan	19 weeks intervention on digital game authoring (DGA)	Quasi-experiment with 1 experiment and 1 compare group; Pre-test/post-test and delayed post-test quantitative measures	Empowered critical thinking, retention of learning content, academic achievement and authentic application of biological knowledge were noticed.
[25], Hong Kong	Nine days of intervention on guided social inquiry learning (GSIL) and flipped social inquiry learning (FSIL)	Quasi-experiment with two treatment conditions; control and experimental groups, qualitative and quantitative measures, post-test only	Participants who received FSIL intervention had more beneficial learning experiences within and without the classroom.
[26], Canada	Six months intervention on arts integrated collective creation (AICC) and educational social enterprise (ESE)	Quasi-experiment with 1 experiment and 1 waitlist control group; pre-test/post -test quantitative measures	Combined treatment (AICC & ESE) showed better scores on social empowerment; increased entrepreneurial spirit evidenced.
[27], USA	Two years of intervention on healthy and empowered youth (HEY) program	Quasi-experiment with single group pre-test post-test qualitative measures n=129	Participants showed increased life skills, confidence, self-esteem and empowered involvement in the community.
[28], USA	Four years intervention on youth empowerment solution (YES) to develop positive development	Quasi-experiment with modified randomized control and experimental group with pre-test/post-test quantitative measures	Results indicate positive influence of empowering process on youth development.
[29], Indonesia	Two sessions of expository lessons on enhancing scientific thinking	Quasi-experiment; purposive sampling; pre-test/post-test; quantitative measures	Scientific enquiry is characterized by observation, identifying the problem, formulation of hypotheses, analysis of data and arriving at conclusion.
[30], USA	11-week intervention on self-regulated empowered program (SREP)	Quasi-random sampling, pre-test/post-test quantitative	Self-regulated intervention program was perceived to have empowering effects.
[31], Indonesia	Eight sessions of intervention to compare the effect of group investigation (GI) and think talk and write (TTW)	Quasi-experiment with experiment and control groups pre-test/post-test quantitative measures; Simple random sampling	Participants taught by GI and TTW strategies showed an empowered and higher grade of metacognitive skills than those taught by conventional strategy.
[32], Australia	10 weeks of IGNITE program for high ability underachievers	Quasi-experiment with two treatment conditions with no control group; pre-test/post-test quantitative measures	Both interventions showed increased self-efficacy, self and environmental perception, acceptance of one's ability and improved goal valuation.
[33], not stated	Two days Intervention program on positive masculinity, emotional awareness	Quasi-experiment; single treatment group with pre-test/post-test and follow up quantitative measures	The intervention empowered participants to engage positively in masculinity issues from an early age.
[34], Portugal	Eight weeks of intervention of two different approaches to teaching	Quasi-experiment with pre-test/post-test Quantitative measures with two compare groups; Convenient sampling	The study showed that the sports education approach was effective in enhancing students' empowerment and self-confidence.
[35], USA	10 months intervention on comprehensive physical education class	Non-randomized control trial, convenient sampling; control and experimental groups with follow up measures	The intervention positively affected the participants' daily steps in the physical education class and moderate to vigorous physical activities.
[36], Sri Lanka	Eight weeks of intervention on dengue-carrying mosquito control education	Quasi-experiment; Pre-test/post-test quantitative measures with 2 experimental groups vs 1 control group	The intervention resulted in 73% and 61% reduction of dengue fever cases in urban and rural areas respectively.

2.5. Summarizing and reporting results

The fifth stage of the scoping review, according to Arksey and O' Malley [16] consists of collating, summarizing, and reporting results. The following section seeks to provide an overview of the literature reviewed. However, this section does not synthesize the evidence or combine the conclusions from different studies. The findings are presented as a narrative account based on thematic construction.

3. RESULTS

In this section we briefly summarize the findings of the reviewed articles. As indicated in Figure 1, 1,684 studies were identified from different databases and source, out of which 16 studies fulfilled inclusion criteria. The sources of these 16 researches were: Microsoft Academics (n=2), PubMed (n=1), Google Scholar (n=6), JSTOR (n=3), ERIC (n=3) and Other Sources (n=1). Five studies were conducted in the USA, two studies in Indonesia and one each in Australia, Canada, Hong Kong, Israel, Nigeria, Norway, Portugal, Sri Lanka and Taiwan. While most of these studies were conducted in Asia and North America, the absence of literature in South America was identified. While a range of studies focused on technology-assisted empowered learning [21]–[24], a number of studies had their focus on socially empowered learning [25]–[28]. Fewer studies targeted cognitive empowerment of students [29]–[31], whereas the remaining studies were spread across empowered learning in relation to psychological education [32], [33], sports education [34], [35], and health education [36].

3.1. How is empowered learning conceptualized within the literature pertaining to school-level education?

To gain a deeper understanding of the conceptual framework we examined how the concept of empowered learning is theorized in the reviewed studies. The majority of the studies (n=10) did not specify any definition of the concept of empowered learning, while the concept of empowered learning did not vary considerably in papers that defined it although it was viewed from different perspectives. Empowerment is a process that enables an individual to gain autonomy and determination to attain one's goals and represent one's interests [34]. Scientific thinking empowerment is termed as the ability to seek knowledge by way of enquiry, investigation, inference and argument. The inquiry stage includes determining the purpose of the activities, data identification, relating the findings to the primary knowledge and problem formulation. Analysis results in displaying the obtained knowledge in the previous stage; inference compiles data and draws conclusion and argument provides reliability to the given statement [29].

From a psychological perspective, empowerment was defined as a process whereby an individual thinks highly about one's ability to exercise control and make meaningful changes in oneself and society [22]. Metacognitive empowerment in learning is conceptualized as the result of the ability to make decisions and choose the right strategy. Learners whose metacognitive skills are developed can take responsibility for their own learning and choose the appropriate learning strategies to complete a given task. Development of metacognitive skill empowerment is crucial to learners as it enables learners to evolve into self-regulated learners and to manage their own thinking and learning. The application of the suitable teaching strategies is one of the elements producing the development and empowerment of learners' metacognitive skills [31]. Self-regulated empowerment can be achieved by a number of steps taken by a learner to accept ownership of one's learning by vigorously engaging in learning to overcoming problem. Self-regulation and motivation act together to promote learners' empowerment where learners seek social support and acceptance of peers during the course of their learning [32].

Socially empowered learning is a project comprising creative and agency-based activities related to real-world issues with a focus on creating an effective social impact. Teachers can increase a student's social empowerment through collective efficacy as studies on social learning theories indicate that collective empowerment can be attained with social activities in groups, particularly for learners in conditions that seem socially unfair. Social empowerment reflects perceived general efficiency of the group [26]. One study [23] referred to empowered learning as a process by which a student obtains the skill of self-direction and the potentiality of further progress. Empowerment is described as a product of interpersonal, interactional and behavioral components [28]. Masculinity empowerment can be achieved by providing programs that positively thrust emphasis on males' strengths to move away from what is wrong in them. Masculinity empowerment results in male telling the truth, exhibiting courage, resilience, service, perseverance, and problem solving [33].

3.2. What are the features and scope of the interventions directed towards empowered learning of students at the school level education?

3.2.1. In-depth design

All the studies included in this scoping review relied exclusively on quasi-experimental research design to measure the effect of various interventions on students' empowered learning at school level education. In terms of method, a large number of studies (n=8) used quantitative methods while three studies employed mixed-method and one study [27] collected qualitative data. In the 16 studies selected for the review, the sample size ranged from 10 to 3294. Concerning sampling, 12 studies applied random sampling, whereas one study [29] used purposive sampling, one study [34] applied convenient sampling, and one study [21] used a multistage sampling design. Most studies used control groups; six studies did not, while one study [26] had a waitlist control group. All studies, except for one study [29], had equivalent groups. The majority of the studies (n=12) measured pre-test and post-test scores; two studies measured only post-test scores; one study [24] measured pre-test, post-test, and delayed post-test scores, and one study [35] measured daily aggregate scores.

3.2.2. Duration and frequency of interventions

The range of empowered learning interventions reviewed here spans between two days and four years. A diverse range of frequency of the interventions was identified. There were three studies had an intervention daily, five studies held interventions every week, and two studies conducted interventions twice a week. The remaining six studies did not mention the frequency of interventions. The duration of each session of intervention ranged between 45 and 90 minutes.

3.2.3. Topics and teaching methods

It is evident from the current scoping review that the researchers implemented interventions on different topics and methods to facilitate empowered learning. Topics addressed in the studies mainly covered art education and entrepreneurial coaching [26] and interventions on substance abuse and sex education [35]. Several studies focused entirely on one single theme-critical thinking [24], positive social behavior [28], scientific thinking skills [29], gender role program [33], sports education [34] and health-related interventions [36]. Methods of teaching included traditional teaching, technology-aided intervention, after school program, worksheet, physical activity, differentiated instruction, group investigation with conventional teaching, field trips and guest lectures.

3.2.4. Tools of data collection

Tools used to obtain quantitative and qualitative data varied as per the need, subject matter and feasibility of the studies reviewed. In general, a vast number of studies (n=8) utilized a questionnaire for data collection while other studies used tools such as history achievement test [21], class tests [30], [31] and secondary sources [36]. In addition, there were three studies which used multiple tools to collect data: questionnaire, observation and semi-structured interviews [22], pedometers and Gopher FIT step pros [35], and questionnaire and interview [25], [27].

3.2.5. Ethical consideration

Providing sufficient information and obtaining permission from the participants is a good practice in research. In this regard, the reviewed studies had two different approaches. While few studies (n=4) obtained informed consent of the participants, several studies (n=12) either did not obtain informed consent or did not state it in the report of their studies.

3.3. How is the role of students' empowered learning within school level education viewed by the researchers in general?

Empowerment has certainly become a significant concept in educational policies [37]. Empowered learners are highly motivated to complete given tasks, they are competent in the classroom, find meaning in the assigned tasks and they can create an impact on the learning process. When teachers make the appropriate content related to students' feelings of competence, meaningfulness and impact, students feel more empowered to learn [38]. Empowering school environment provide learners choices in their learning to solve problems; develop personal meaning; and become more competent and independent decision-makers [39].

Many studies support that, in schools, empowered learning occurs when students meet their specific needs and associate with others to achieve a common goal [6], [40]. In this scoping review, empowered learning is viewed as an essential factor that influences academic success. Empowered education supports students to achieve success in a collaborative environment through self-confidence, self-direction, cooperation and communication [34]. Empowered learners are more likely to actively engage in the learning

process, face challenging opportunities and possess greater potentials to have control or to make positive changes in their lives [22]. For a student to be empowered in metacognitive skills, the implementation of the most suitable teaching strategies is necessary. Furthermore, the absence of empowerment in students' metacognitive skills causes lower learning outcomes [31]. Socially empowered learners show not only remarkable confidence in performing given tasks, but they are also confident in performing future dissimilar tasks. These two abilities encourage students to generate an entrepreneurial spirit, innovation, strong willpower to make decisions when faced with adversity, and increased intellectual engagement in the learning process [26]. Empowered learning creates in students a desire to impact the world; take independent decisions; think critically, and use their abilities in real-life situations [28]. Empowerment in school setting may be considered as a result of reflective processes through which students obtain the power of self-direction and the prospect of more freedom [23].

4. DISCUSSION

This scoping review has tried to provide an all-inclusive summary of various programs in schools on empowered learning. The school setting is generally recognized as an essential field that highly influences learner empowerment's academic and social domains [6]. While the reviewed studies were spread across different countries, it is observed that no empirical studies were reported from countries of the South American continent. Each of the reviewed studies focused on a specific empowered learning component such as social, technology-assisted, cognitive, psychological, sports and health.

4.1. Empowered learning as a concept

Empowerment is not an accidental outcome but it is an intended outcome. It is a multi-level concept which includes personal, psychological, organizational and community elements [28]. This study indicates that the conceptualization of empowered learning, though lacking in many studies, did not vary considerably. Although few studies attempted to define empowered learning, the lack of commonly accepted definition of empowered learning is an issue that gives a clarion call for researchers to define it in a school setting. However, in general, empowered learning is viewed as enabling individuals to gain autonomy and determination to achieve their goals and represent their interests. This standpoint is supported by other studies which focused on the personal and inter-personal elements of empowered learning. This points to the fact that the concept of empowered learning in schools includes intertwining of personal and interpersonal features of a learner [28].

4.2. Features and scope of interventions

Although true experiments in which the samples are randomly allocated have a higher possibility of yielding reliable results [41], this may not be viable in every context. Our review identified the absence of pure experimental intervention to enhance the empowered learning of students at school level education. However, the studies that used a quasi-experimental design have produced desired results. A strong point of this review is that it has identified the absence of pure experimental intervention, a gap that invites researchers' consideration while planning future studies. Furthermore, researchers have conducted numerous studies utilizing qualitative and quantitative methods and, in many cases, a combination of both. Though there is a wide gap between qualitative and quantitative methods, scholars accept both these methods' validity as this gap is beneficial in facilitating information acquisition [42], as there are no absolute rubrics for deciding whether a specific research method is ethical or not [43].

As stated in the results, in order to measure empowered learning, researchers relied on three methods; qualitative, quantitative and mixed-methods, resulting in the authenticity of the result obtained. In this review, while the sample size ranged from 10 to 3,294, various sampling methods such as random sampling, purposive sampling, convenient sampling, multistage sampling were identified. However, probability random sampling is preferred for more accurate generalization [44] as the non-probability sampling method normally takes in judgment [45]. Researchers in behavioral science widely use Pre-test-post-test design to measure the change of experimental treatment [46]. However, some studies considered for this review measured only post-test scores, while one study each measured delayed pre-test scores and daily aggregate scores. Though the duration of the intervention is an important determinant of the effectiveness of the intervention [47], it is difficult to arrive at a conclusion about the most appropriate duration of intervention. The duration of the intervention on empowered learning reviewed in this study ranged from two days to four years, while the duration of each session of intervention ranged between 45 to 90 minutes.

The studies in this scoping review, ensuring the applicability of the theory, followed a method where the participants were given exercises and activities related to empowered learning within and without classrooms, resulting in positive changes. The validity and reliability of the data are the crucial indicators of the quality of a measuring tool, though several factors may influence the accuracy of the collected data [48].

In this study, conclusive evidence is found that authors collected data using different tools (questionnaires, observation and semi-structured interviews, historical achievement tests, class tests, and secondary sources).

Applying suitable ethical values is imperative in protecting human subjects in all research studies wherein all participants agree to give informed consent. Participants need to be sufficiently informed about the research and their freedom to involve or decline from the study [49]. While applying the ethics of research, a great deal of attention needs to be paid to principles of autonomy, justice, confidentiality, non-deception and the deterrence of psychological or physical harm [50]. Despite this, of all the 16 studies reviewed, four studies explicitly discussed the informed consent taken from the participants. However, we observed that 12 studies had not stated ethical considerations.

4.3. Role of empowered learning

If learners gain empowerment together with confidence to act, they will, in all probability, assimilate the process, be more engaged in challenging opportunities and have greater control over their own lives [34]. Providing a platform for empowered learning seemed to be as straightforward an aim as is seen in all the studies reviewed. Many papers highlighted the significance of empowered learning in a school setting and its association with the personal and academic development of the learner. Specific emphasis was placed on the need for socially empowered learning to mold learners into individuals who perform given tasks confidently with an entrepreneurial spirit and increased intellectual engagement. It is important to note that the relation between empowered learning and academic and personal excellence was clear in some studies while creating empowered learners was seen as shaping successful individuals who make a difference in the world by being able to take independent decisions critically in real-life situations. Additionally, a collaborative environment in school coupled with self-confidence and a sense of direction creates more empowered learners in society. Furthermore, a direct positive relationship between the instructional strategy of the teacher and the empowered learning of students has also been observed, which suggests the use of an appropriate type of instruction in the classroom.

4.4. Implications of the findings

The substantial strength of this study is that it reviewed only intervention studies. This study is significant as it is one of the first to review intervention studies on empowered learning in schools. The findings of the study are robust since this review has charted, collated and summarized literature. The interplay between better academic performance and curriculum based on empowered learning is evidenced in all the literature studied in this review. This provides key recommendations to educationists to facilitate the empowered learning of students.

We acknowledge that this review is not free from limitations. In respect to the coverage, this study included English articles only from specific databases and sources. Theses, working papers, white papers, unpublished works and the studies published before the year 1995 were excluded. In addition, we omitted interventions conducted in pre-schools and primary schools. These criteria of omitting probable and relevant studies may have influenced the conclusions of this review. Moreover, this review included interventional studies only and did not make a comparative evaluation of the various interventions reviewed. Future scoping reviews on empowered learning could include studies published in non-English languages and non-intervention studies.

Though researchers have referred to empowered learning as a concept, this study points out that there is no commonly accepted theory of empowered learning as a single concept. This study calls for further research to develop commonly accepted definitions of empowered learning of students in the school context and more pure experimental research to create empowered learners. Further, literature from non-intervention studies, unpublished works, and non-English publication could be studied to arrive at a more accurate conclusion.

5. CONCLUSION

It is becoming evident that empowered learning can positively influence the academic accomplishment of students in school settings. Empowered learning is associated with students' ability to actively participate in the learning process, confront challenging opportunities and make positive changes in their lives. Nevertheless, there is a threat of educators developing a pedagogy not fully understanding the elements that result in learner empowerment. The pedagogy framed by educators should consider students' active engagement that facilitates empowered learning within and without the classroom. Since previous researches have seldom reviewed intervention studies on empowered learning, this review can support educationists in implementing school-based intervention programs to promote empowered learning.

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BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Anto Titus is a Doctoral candidate, School of Education, Christ University, Bangalore, India. He has over 15 years of experience as an academican at St. Francis group of institutions, Bangalore. His research focusses on Differentiated Instruction, Empowered learning and Reflective Thinking at school level Education. Presently he serves as the Principal of St. Francis PU College, Bangalore. He can be contacted at email: titusanto@gmail.com.

Peter Varkey Muttungal is a Director and Assistant Professor at School of Education, Christ University holds M. Phil and PhD in Education. He serves as the research supervisor to Doctoral candidates at Christ University. His research interests are in the areas of educational leadership and management, organizational culture and teacher education process. Presently, he also serves as the Principal of Christ PU College-Evening and Finance Administrator of Christ Junior College. Apart from teaching and research, Dr. Peter has been into educational administration, in a diverse socio-economic setting for several years. He can be contacted at email: peter.mv@christuniversity.in.